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REPORT

on the results of the project

**ANALYSIS OF PEDAGOGICAL STUDIES OF THE UKRAINIAN FREE UNIVERSITY
IN GERMANY**

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Abstract

The relevance of this study is driven by the need for self-sufficient teachers who can work with children experiencing varying degrees of trauma and stress, as well as the potential for implementing positive practices of teacher training at the Ukrainian Free University (UFU) in Germany.

Objective: To explore the educational design of teacher training within the master's and doctoral programs at the Ukrainian Free University, and to formulate recommendations for Ukrainian higher pedagogical institutions regarding the implementation of UFU's best practices in fostering teacher agency.

Methods: The study employs analysis of scientific sources on the research problem, content analysis of relevant documents and teaching materials, SWOT analysis, observation, interviews, systematization, and generalization. These methods help to determine the structural features of teacher education and formulate recommendations for incorporating UFU's positive practices into master's and doctoral teacher training programs in Ukraine.

Results: From a cultural and historical perspective, the study identifies UFU as the first and only Ukrainian higher education institution abroad, one of Germany's oldest private universities, meeting German university standards by integrating scientific research with education and engaging students in academic activities while adhering to Western university education principles. The specific features of UFU's pedagogical studies are shaped by its historical development. From an informational content perspective, the study analyzes the educational and research components of UFU's pedagogical programs, including the academic and methodological support for master's and doctoral pedagogy courses, as well as the role of the library and archives in shaping the learning environment. From a subject-process perspective, the study investigates the characteristics of the

teacher training process, conducting a content analysis of its key features and a SWOT analysis of teacher training in the context of digitalization.

Conclusions: The Ukrainian Free University is a unique educational institution that combines Ukrainian pedagogical traditions with European standards. Its historical journey highlights the importance of preserving academic freedom and national identity in emigration contexts, while its distinguished figures have laid the foundation for pedagogical studies focused on humanistic values and the formation of the Ukrainian educational ideal. UFU's uniqueness is reflected in its preservation of pedagogical traditions while fostering contemporary teaching innovations, the emphasis on inclusive education and psychological-pedagogical support for children with traumatic experiences (particularly in wartime conditions), the possibility of obtaining an additional specialization, and its multicultural nature. The findings of the DAAD research project "Analysis of Pedagogical Studies at the Ukrainian Free University" confirm the formation of self-sufficient educators capable of upholding national identity, applying critical thinking, implementing innovative teaching approaches, and working in multicultural environments. This underscores the significance of UFU's experience for the development of Ukrainian pedagogy in the face of global challenges and European integration, as reflected in the formulated recommendations.

Keywords: Ukrainian Free University, pedagogical studies, transformative pedagogy, positive experience, development of teacher agency.

Table of Contents

Introduction	5
Pedagogical Studies at UFU in a Cultural-Historical Perspective	10
Pedagogical Studies at UFU in an Informational-Content Perspective	15
Pedagogical Studies at UFU in a Subject-Process Perspective	28
Recommendations for Ukrainian Higher Pedagogical Institutions on Implementing the Positive Experience of Developing Teacher Agency at UFU	36
Publication and dissemination of project results	38
Establishing international cooperation	44
Conclusions	45
References	50
Appendices	54

Introduction

In the context of war, the role of the Ukrainian pedagogical community, which ensures the socialization and upbringing of children and youth, becomes critically important for societal development. Particular attention is required for fostering the agency of educators in general secondary education institutions. According to data from the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, at the onset of the war in the first half of 2022, over 670,000 students and 25,000 teachers left Ukraine (Kabanets, 2022). Consequently, the task emerged of collaborating with the governments of various countries and ensuring the inclusion of a Ukrainian studies component. Ukrainian experts have identified the need for self-reliant teachers capable of working with children exhibiting varying degrees of trauma and stress.

The laws of Ukraine “On Education” (2017), “On Higher Education” (2014), and the “Conceptual Foundations of Pedagogical Education in Ukraine and Its Integration into the European Educational Space” (2004) outline the requirements for the quality of training future teachers. The Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in Ukraine for 2022–2032, aimed at achieving the strategic goal of “Internationalization of Ukrainian Higher Education,” includes operational objectives such as the adoption of the best foreign educational practices in Ukraine, increasing the number of international educational and scientific collaboration projects, and integrating scientific and academic staff into the global scientific community (Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in Ukraine for 2022–2032, 2022). Thus, studying the experience of teacher training in universities across European Union countries is a priority for the successful integration into the European educational space and the fulfillment of Ukraine’s national objectives.

In this regard, the study and implementation of positive practices in teacher training at the Ukrainian Free University (UFU, Munich, Germany) are relevant both

for Ukraine and for other countries currently providing assistance to its citizens. The university has long established itself as an innovative hub of Ukrainian education abroad, offering educational programs that blend Ukrainian traditions with European educational standards. Its unique experience merits attention, particularly in the context of its active engagement at the intersection of two cultures and its provision of opportunities for high-quality pedagogical education that considers global trends, the specifics of Ukrainian culture, and the needs of the diaspora.

The theoretical and methodological aspects of the Western system of pedagogical education have been explored by N. Avshenyuk, L. Zyazyun, N. Nychkalo, L. Pukhivska, S. Kohut, O. Lokshyna, and others. Studies on foreign experiences in teacher training have been presented in the works of V. Bauer, N. Zhuravska, Ye. Neroba, O. Ohienko, T. Osadcha, and others. The preparation of educators in Germany has been the focus of research by N. Abashkina, O. Haiduk, L. Diachenko, N. Kish, L. Pasichnyk, O. Melnyk, O. Pryshliak, and others. The foundation for scientific inquiries into the training of future teachers in Germany is provided by the works of German researchers whose scientific investigations center on this topic, including H. Altrichter, S. Blömeke, F. Weinert, M. Winter, H. Hentig, W. Klafki, R. Messner, S. Robinsohn, A. Nolle, and E. Terhart. Aspects of the development and activities of the Ukrainian Free University (UFU) have been elucidated in publications by I. Mirchuk, A. Kokosh, M. Pryshliak, L. Rudnytskyi, T. SydorhukPotulnytska, M. Shafoval, and others.

The project aims to investigate the features of the educational design of teacher training within the master's and doctoral programs at the Ukrainian Free University, and to formulate recommendations for Ukrainian higher pedagogical education institutions regarding the implementation of positive experiences from the UFU in fostering educators' agency.

The study employed methods such as analysis of scientific sources related to the research problem, examination of relevant documents and educational methodological materials, content analysis, SWOT analysis, observation, interviewing, systematization, and generalization. These methods were used to identify the specific characteristics of the structure of pedagogical education and to formulate recommendations for integrating the UFU's positive practices into the training of educators in Ukraine at the master's and doctoral levels.

The research project titled “Analysis of Pedagogical Studies at the Ukrainian Free University in Germany,” conducted under the DAAD programme “Future of Ukraine: Research Grants for Ukrainian Master's Students and Researchers,” consisted of three stages: preparatory, main, and concluding. During the preparatory stage (December 2024 – January 2025), scientific studies on pedagogical education in Germany were analyzed with a focus on key trends in teacher training.

During the preparatory stage, attention was focused on the fact that modern approaches to the development of pedagogical education in Germany hold significant importance for reforming this field in Ukraine, necessitating an analysis of the German experience. The authors of the monograph *Competency-Based Approach to Teacher Training in Foreign Countries: Theory and Practice* emphasize that one of the leading trends in the development of pedagogical education in Germany is the active introduction and implementation of a competency-based model for teacher preparation (Avshenyuk et al., 2014). Among the promising directions for the development of pedagogical education in Germany within the context of creating a European Higher Education Area, N. Kish highlights the trend of incorporating a European dimension into the content of teachers' professional training (Kish, 2016).

The main stage was implemented at the Ukrainian Free University (Munich, Germany) over a one-month period from January 29, 2025, to February 28, 2025.

During this time at the UFU, the educational programs for master's and doctoral degrees in pedagogy, along with their components (academic disciplines), were analyzed. The relevant scientific-informational and educational-methodological resources were examined, in-depth interviews were conducted with university leadership, structural unit representatives, faculty, and students, and the role of the university library as an entity in designing the educational environment for teacher training was investigated. Archival materials and publications concerning the establishment and development of pedagogical studies at the UFU were also analyzed. The signing of an Agreement on International Cooperation between the Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine and the Ukrainian Free University (Germany) was organized.

At the generalization stage (March 2025 – April 2025), recommendations were formulated regarding the consideration of the positive practices of UFU in the training of teachers in Ukraine under master's and doctoral programs, an article was published in English and Ukrainian in the professional journal of Ukraine “Professional Pedagogics” (Romanova, 2025a), an article in Ukrainian in the journal “Herald of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine” (Romanova, 2025c), an interview with the Rector of UFU, Prof. Larysa Didkovska, in the Zenodo repository “Herald of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine” (Romanova, 2025b), a project page was created on the website of the Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine (Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, n.d.), and a report was prepared.

Information on the project's progress was shared on the Facebook social network (9 posts; <https://www.facebook.com/anna.romanova.7564>).

In accordance with the project's goals and objectives, its implementation at the UFU can be viewed through several perspectives: cultural-historical (the

establishment and development of pedagogical studies, the influence of prominent faculty figures), informational-content (educational and academic programs, scientific-informational and educationalmethodological resources), and subject-processual (classroom observations, in-depth interviews).

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the team at the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD) for the opportunity to implement this project, and to Ms. Anna Heinz personally for her consultations and coordination of my activities. I sincerely thank the creative team of the Ukrainian Free University for their help and support in conducting this research, especially Rector, Dr. of Psychology, Prof. Larysa Didkovska, Chancellor Dmytro Shevchenko, Head of the Department of Pedagogy, Dr. of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Svitlana Kohut, Faculty of the Department of Pedagogy, Dr. of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Dina Shulzhenko, Dr. Peter Hiltes, Project Manager, Dr. Lilia Bondarenko, Referent of Academic and Student Affairs Dr. Roman Tyutenko, Head of the Library Ivan Zarytsky, Archivist Yulia Chernomor, students Anna Higl and Victoria Danylevska. I also thank the Director of the Institute of Vocational Education at the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, Dr. of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Full Member (Academician) of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine Valentina Radkevych, Deputy Director for Scientific and Experimental Work, Dr. of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Lyudmila Yershova, Head of the Department of Foreign Professional Education Systems, PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Senior Researcher Svitlana Kravets.

Pedagogical Studies at UFU in a Cultural-Historical Perspective

During the main phase of the study, while working in the library and archive of the Ukrainian Free University (UFU), it was established that, from a historical perspective, this institution is one of the oldest private universities in Germany. Investigating its history, L. Rudnytsky (2011, pp. 88-106) convincingly demonstrates that UFU meets the requirements for German universities in terms of integrating academic research with education, involving students in scholarly activities, and adhering to the principles of Western university education, including scientific rigor, responsibility, independence, honesty and integrity, tolerance, the popularization of scientific knowledge, and collaboration. At the same time, it remains faithful to the ideals of its founders and the principle of academic freedom, functioning as “a university that serves Ukraine and is open to the world.”

UFU is the first and only Ukrainian institution of higher education abroad, and in 2026, it will celebrate its 105th anniversary. The university’s founders, including D. Antonovych, O. Kolessa, I. Horbachevsky, M. Hrushevsky, S. Dnistryansky, S. Rudnytsky, and others, realized a unique vision in the global history of academic institutions: establishing a higher education institution with the right to award doctoral degrees and habilitation outside its homeland and without its support. This was done to preserve the spirit of academic freedom, ensure objective truth in the humanities, and represent the Ukrainian nation. Based on the three European cities associated with the institution’s activities, its development is divided into three periods: the Vienna Period—from 1920 to September 1921; the Prague Period—from October 1921 to mid-May 1945; and the Munich Period— from autumn 1945 to the present (Shafoval, 2011, pp. 1-2, 7-9).

An analysis of UFU’s lecture programs in Prague (1922–1942) revealed that psychological disciplines appeared in the curriculum of the historical-philological

section of the Faculty of Philosophy in 1930 (“Psychology,” 1930–1931; “Fundamental Problems of Psychology,” 1936– 1937), while pedagogical disciplines emerged in 1935 (“Fundamental Problems of Pedagogy,” summer semester of 1935; “Foundations of Pedagogy,” 1937–1938). These courses were authored by Professor Ivan Mirchuk and were taught for 3 hours per week, though they were not included in the curriculum every academic year but rather appeared periodically. In 1939, pedagogy was distinguished as a separate block, developed by Professor Avgustin Voloshyn. This block consisted of two disciplines: “Pedagogical Methodology” (3 hours per week) and “Practical Exercises” (2 hours per week). By the 1942–1943 academic year, the course titles had changed to “Pedagogy. Pedagogical Ethics” and “School Administration.” During this period, psychology was also separated into a distinct block comprising two disciplines (“Introduction to Characterology” and “Psychological Seminar”), developed by Associate Professor O. Ivanov (UFU Archive, Munich, Germany).

The figures of I. Mirchuk and A. Voloshyn merit particular attention. In 1921, I. Mirchuk became an associate professor at the Ukrainian Free University (UFU) in Vienna, and from 1925, he served as a professor, teaching philosophy, ethics, psychology, and pedagogy. After World War II, in 1946, I. Mirchuk played an active role in reviving UFU’s activities in Munich, where he served as rector during various periods. He advocated for the development of a national pedagogy that would account for the specifics of the Ukrainian mentality and history. His pedagogical approach significantly influenced the education of a new generation of intellectuals capable of advancing the Ukrainian nation in exile and on the international stage (Kokosh, pp. 139–154).

A. Voloshyn, the last rector of UFU in Prague, met a tragic end on July 19, 1945, in prison, a victim of Stalinist repression. As noted by T. Bednarzova in the article “Avgustin Voloshyn – The Last Rector of UFU in Prague” (1998), he was a

prominent figure in the state-building efforts of Carpathian Ukraine (1938–1939), opposing Magyar-Russification policies and advocating for Ukrainian as the language of instruction in educational institutions. As a professor at UFU, A. Voloshyn taught psychology, logic, and pedagogical disciplines. His seminal pedagogical work, *Methodology of Teaching* (Voloshyn, 1943), remains relevant to this day for fostering pedagogical thought and teacher creativity. The archive also provided insight into lecture programs from the early Munich Period. Specifically, in the 1946–1947 academic year, the pedagogical block included the disciplines “Teaching Methods” (2 hours per week) and “Practice” (1 hour per week), authored and taught by Professor H. Vashchenko (UFU Archive, Munich, Germany).

Archival materials from the collection of H. Vashchenko, a prominent Ukrainian educator who played a significant role in the development of the pedagogical discipline at the Ukrainian Free University (UFU) in Munich, have been studied. The archive contains the manuscript of a seminal article for Ukrainian pedagogy titled “The Traditional Ukrainian Ideal of a Human Being,” which begins with words that still demand profound reflection: “The foundation of pedagogical work, as its goal, rests upon the ideal of a human being accepted by the pedagogical system employed by a given nation. Due to harsh historical circumstances, the Ukrainian people currently lack their own clearly developed pedagogical system and, consequently, a clearly defined ideal of upbringing. The construction of such a system and the formulation of the human ideal as the goal of upbringing constitute the most critical tasks of contemporary pedagogy” (Vashchenko, 1957). The archival materials of H. Vashchenko also include manuscripts of articles such as “Bolshevik Distortions of Western Pedagogues’ Ideas in the Field of Didactics” (in Ukrainian and German), “Psychology in the Soviet Union” (in German), newspaper articles “Notes on Aesthetics,” “Socialism and Individualism in the Light of Christianity,” “The Third Generation (Grandchildren),” and “Psychology in the Soviet Union” (in

German), as well as the manuscript of the work “On the History of Spiritual Education in PreRevolutionary Russia” (UFU Archive, Munich, Germany).

Evidence of the focus on educational activities at UFU is provided by an analysis of the minutes of the meetings of the Professorial Council of the Philosophical Faculty of UFU. For instance, Minute No. 18 from July 10, 1948, highlights the need to strengthen the educational aspect of the learning process in the spirit of Christianity and national statehood (Minute No. 18, July 10, 1948, UFU Archive, Munich, Germany).

In the context of the development of pedagogical studies, documents from 1947–1948 – when the University continued its operations in Munich after World War II – were examined. These include the Statute (1947), Study Regulations of the Philosophical Faculty (1947), Study Regulations of the Faculty of Law and Socio-Economic Sciences (1948), and requirements for the ordination of associate professors and habilitation (1948). The adoption of these documents was driven by the need to regulate the educational process, which was a prerequisite for obtaining a decree from the Bavarian Ministry of Education and Religion recognizing UFU’s activities, an event that occurred in 1950 (Kokosh, p. 100).

In A. Kokosh’s publication “Institutional Formation of the Ukrainian Free University in Bavaria (1945–1950),” information is systematized regarding the establishment of the Department of Philosophy and Pedagogy within the Philosophical Faculty at the outset of the Munich period, during which the Chair of Pedagogy and Didactics began functioning. The author notes that students could earn a Master’s degree in Philosophy, specializing in pedagogy and psychology, by successfully passing exams in Group A subjects (general), covering fundamental issues of philosophical sciences, general and pedagogical psychology, the history of world and Ukrainian pedagogy, and five Group B subjects (specific), namely pedagogical theory, didactics, school hygiene and school studies, methods of

selected subjects, preschool pedagogy and methods, and extracurricular education. Additionally, they were required to attend two semesters of a pedagogical pro-seminar, three semesters of a pedagogical seminar, and complete a six-month school internship (8 hours per week) in their primary and supplementary disciplines. For students choosing pedagogy as a minor specialization, all subjects except fundamental issues of philosophical sciences, didactics, school hygiene, and school studies were mandatory, along with two semesters of a pedagogical pro-seminar (Kokosh, pp. 103–108).

Thus, the findings from work in the UFU library and archive affirm that the historical context is crucial for understanding the specifics of pedagogical studies at UFU. The development of pedagogy at the University has occurred and continues to occur within a cultural-educational environment shaped by progressive ideas: a general tradition of resisting dogmatism, intolerance, and restrictions on academic freedom, as well as the scholarly contributions of the faculty, such as O. Kolessa's methodology of folk studies, H. Vashchenko's justification of the Ukrainian people's educational ideal, A. Voloshyn's principles of Ukrainian school studies, I. Mirchuk's concepts of national pedagogy, V. Yaniv's establishment of the Pedagogical Institute, and B. Yerzhabkova's research in social pedagogy, among others.

Pedagogical Studies at UFU in an Informational-Content Perspective

The University's name is key to understanding both its free spirit and its sense of being a "territory of freedom," as well as the opportunities for autodidacticism – that is, the faculty's authorship in shaping the content, methods, forms, and technologies of education, and the proactive engagement of students in selecting courses, assignments, and implementing projects. Today, UFU students can pursue studies in 13 specialties, among which pedagogy remains one of the most popular.

The objective of the master's program is to provide students with the opportunity to deepen their knowledge in their chosen disciplines and to explore various issues within historical and contemporary contexts. The priority focus is on Ukraine in Europe, examining Ukrainian science, education, language, culture, literature, society, law, and economy in this light. Within the framework of the master's program, students can also obtain qualifications in specialized fields of knowledge, such as interdisciplinary programs in Ukrainian studies and international relations, including German-Ukrainian or Ukrainian-German relations within a broader European context.

Admission requirements for the program include possession of a bachelor's degree or an equivalent diploma from an accredited higher education institution; proficiency in the Ukrainian language sufficient for writing essays, understanding texts, lectures, questions, and discussions; knowledge of German or English at least at the level of text comprehension, though comprehension of lectures is desirable; two recommendation letters from the applicant's previous educational institution, with the option to include additional recommendation letters from an employer; and a motivation essay in which the applicant explains why they chose the Ukrainian Free University (UFU), their long-term plans, what they intend to study, how

studying at UFU will help them achieve their goals, what research they have completed, and what practical knowledge they have acquired thus far.

The requirements of the master's program (120 credits) for students with a four-year bachelor's degree (240 credits) typically entail six semesters of study (17 courses with additional requirements), culminating in a master's thesis and a final examination. In line with the Bologna Process, master's students follow a modular system of study units, which may consist of relevant and related courses and disciplines. For instance, students at the Faculty of Philosophy may choose pedagogy as a core module or as an additional one. Master's students select their modular courses independently, except for the mandatory introductory course in methodology. They must earn 60% of their total credit points in their "core module," with each module carrying 4 credits.

According to the regulations, instructors are required to inform master's students at the first lecture about the course requirements: mandatory literature; the scope and deadlines for essays; the format of oral seminar presentations; the type of exams (oral or written) and their timing (which must occur after the completion of all coursework). Oral exams at UFU last 15-30 minutes, while written exams last 45-60 minutes. It is noted that exams may be substituted with other assessment tools, and final essays and exams may not account for more than 40% of the course grade.

Students in the program fulfill additional program requirements, such as completing an individual project, an internship, or an additional course. The regulations of the master's program emphasize individualized learning, enabling students to independently prepare for academic work and deepen their knowledge in a specific field of study, though this is not mandatory. Master's students wishing to conduct independent research select their own topics. They are permitted a maximum of two individual courses and are encouraged to choose research topics

aligned with their “core module” (primary discipline) or “additional module” (supplementary discipline).

Thus, the substantive components of the master’s program include the course “Methodology of Academic Writing” (4 credits); 16 advanced courses (10 in the primary specialization, 4 in the supplementary specialization, 2 elective courses, and 1 course or internship, totaling 64 credits); the master’s thesis (30 credits); and the defense and final examination (20 credits). Master’s students may opt for two independent research projects in place of a proseminar or seminar course. Assessment is conducted according to the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS).

In terms of upholding academic integrity standards, it is emphasized that cheating during exams results in a failing grade (F) for the exam; a second instance of cheating leads to expulsion from the university; plagiarism or the use of unauthorized aids during essay writing or presentation preparation results in a failing grade (F) for those assignments. A second violation of the rules results in a failing grade (F) for the entire course. A repeated instance of plagiarism leads to expulsion from the university, while purchasing or verbatim copying of essays from the internet or other accessible sources results in immediate expulsion.

The master’s program involves the defense of a master’s thesis and the completion of a final master’s examination, which concludes all ongoing exams and assessments. The master’s thesis must demonstrate in-depth academic research on a chosen topic and consolidate the theoretical knowledge acquired during the program. Completing the thesis serves as evidence of the student’s ability to select and analyze a scientific or practical problem, draw conclusions and generalizations, or substantiate specific recommendations of a theoretical or practical nature. The regulations stipulate that each master’s thesis must contain at least a minor element of originality. Master’s students may write their theses in Ukrainian, English, or

German, with a summary required in Ukrainian (the chosen language must be one in which the thesis advisor, reviewers, and examiners are proficient).

Regarding the thesis preparation process, the following key aspects are outlined:

- The master's student submits the thesis topic for approval only after earning 50% of the required credit points;

- The student independently selects a thesis advisor and topic, then completes and obtains approval for the "Master's Project Form" from the advisor and a representative of the Academic Degree Committee (the dean or deputy dean);

- The thesis must be completed within one semester, or two at most;

- The thesis typically ranges from 60 to 100 pages;

- The student must submit the final version of the thesis electronically to the dean or deputy dean for plagiarism checks, then to the advisor for review, and sign a declaration confirming that the thesis was written independently, using only the cited resources, and has not been submitted to another examination board or institution or previously published. Submission of false declarations results in the thesis being disqualified and the student's expulsion from the university.

The evaluation of a master's thesis is conducted by the academic supervisor, who confirms that the thesis is ready for further review. Following this, the dean or their deputy appoints a second reviewer. A period of six weeks is allocated for the evaluation of the thesis. In cases where the evaluations are highly divergent and one of them is unsatisfactory, the dean, as a representative of the Commission, or their deputy, appoints a third expert reviewer. Reviewers may include professors of the Ukrainian Free University (UFU), associate professors, emeritus professors (senior professors who continue their academic work), honorary professors, and lecturers holding a doctoral degree or a Candidate of Sciences degree. The regulations stipulate that, in exceptional cases, a professor, associate professor, or lecturer from

another higher education institution may be appointed as a reviewer, provided the thesis topic aligns with their professional and academic qualifications and they have at least three years of teaching experience. If the final evaluation of the master's thesis is "unsatisfactory," the master's student is entitled to write a new thesis on a different topic. Failure to pass the master's thesis a second time results in expulsion from the master's program.

The thesis defense lasts 30 minutes and includes a concise and clear statement by the student of the research problem, justification of its relevance, definition of the thesis objectives, methods for achieving them, and presentation of conclusions, recommendations, and the novelty of the work. The student is required to answer the examiners' questions regarding the thesis, provide additional clarifications, and respond to the reviewers' critical remarks.

The content of the final master's examination pertains to the disciplines of the "core module" and the "supplementary module." The examination may be written or oral. Written exams take place prior to the thesis defense. The oral examination occurs immediately after the defense and is conducted by two examiners, one of whom is typically the academic supervisor; the dean or their deputy records the proceedings of the exam.

The overall grade for the master's examination is calculated as the sum of all grades received for the modular course exams (i.e., courses with four credit points), independent research, and the results of the master's examination and thesis.

The regulations for master's studies outline cases in which an examination may be declared invalid if the student deliberately engages in deceit, including falsification of documents or exam results, use of unauthorized aids during the exam, or plagiarism in the master's thesis. In such instances, the Commission has full authority to declare the exam failed. As a consequence, any prior certification of the exam is annulled, and the student is stripped of their diploma.

It is worth noting that certain provisions regarding the training of master's students at UFU are also applicable to doctoral students. This includes requirements for recommendation letters and the language of instruction for admission, opportunities for independent selection of core and supplementary specializations, research topics, and supervisors, the procedure for appointing reviewers, and the promotion of academic integrity policies. Further attention will be focused on the key features of doctoral studies at UFU.

The Doctoral Studies Regulations (Ukrainian Free University, 2024c) consist of the following sections: "Introductory Note"; "Academic Degrees"; "Commission for the Awarding of Academic Degrees"; "Admission Requirements for Doctoral Programs"; "Doctoral Program Requirements"; "Dissertation"; "Dissertation Supervisors"; "Conditions for Admission to Promotion"; "Admission to Promotion"; "Reviewers and Examiners"; "Dissertation Evaluation"; "Dissertation Reviews"; "Third Reviewer and Overall Dissertation Grade"; "Oral Examination (Rigorosum or Defense)"; "Absence, Refusal, Deception, Breach of Procedure"; "Final Examination Result"; "Retaking the Examination"; "Submission of Required Dissertation Copies"; "Doctoral Diploma and Use of the Academic Degree"; "Non-Completion of Promotion and Revocation of the Academic Degree"; "Awarding of Honorary Degrees Dr.phil.h.c. and Dr.Oec.pol.h.c."; "Effective Date of Transitional Provisions." The academic component of training for Doctors of Philosophy, as outlined in the Doctoral Studies Regulations, is also governed by the "Procedure for Awarding a Doctoral Degree" (Ukrainian Free University, 2024b).

At the Faculty of Philosophy, where a pedagogical specialization is obtained, UFU awards the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Doctor philosophiae or Dr. phil. UFU). The regulations emphasize that the doctoral degree is both an educational and academic degree of the third level of higher education, building on a master's degree or a Candidate of Sciences degree. The doctoral degree signifies that the doctoral

candidate has mastered a specific field of knowledge, thoroughly studied the topic or subject of their specialization, opened a new field of research, conducted an analysis, and provided an innovative interpretation or novel solutions to significant issues within their area of specialization.

It should be noted that eligibility for admission to the doctoral program is granted to individuals who have obtained a master's degree from the Ukrainian Free University, a German university, or a foreign university recognized in Germany, or a Candidate of Sciences degree from a recognized university in Ukraine; can demonstrate a high level of academic performance in their prior studies (80% or higher); and have received a high evaluation for their thesis and its defense (80% or higher).

The UFU doctoral program entails three years of study and includes the following components: coursework; doctoral research (dissertation); an examination in philosophy (for the Faculty of Philosophy and the Faculty of Ukrainian Studies); and an oral doctoral examination (defense or *rigorosum*). Doctoral students are required to complete a mandatory course in methodology, seven advanced courses in their primary specialization, and two courses in a supplementary specialization.

A doctoral candidate may begin preparing their dissertation project after successfully completing 60% of the coursework requirements of the doctoral program.

The doctoral candidate submits to the dean, as the representative of the Chair of the Commission, the topic of the doctoral dissertation and a dissertation project for approval. This project must include a hypothesis, an explanation of the significance and relevance of the dissertation topic, its novelty, the structure of the work, and a list of sources and bibliography.

During the writing of the dissertation, the doctoral candidate must demonstrate the ability to conduct independent scientific research, analyze material, delve deeply

into their chosen topic, and present the novelty of their dissertation. The dissertation must be an original work that the doctoral candidate has neither previously published nor defended. It is desirable for the dissertation to have a comparative character. A scientific work lacking a significant element of novelty and analysis will be rejected. The dissertation must comprise at least 150 pages of main text.

Prerequisites for admission to the doctoral promotion include: completion of the coursework requirements of the doctoral program with grades in the candidate's primary specialization of at least "very good" / "B" (1.5 or better); study at the Ukrainian Free University for a minimum of three semesters, each involving the completion of three courses; selection of a dissertation topic aligned with the candidate's specialization; certification that the doctoral candidate is worthy of holding a doctoral degree and has not taken a doctoral examination at another institution of higher education.

For admission to the promotion, the doctoral candidate submits to the dean, as the representative of the Chair of the Commission, the dissertation text in electronic form for plagiarism checks; a review from the academic supervisor; a personally signed statement affirming that the work was completed independently and without external assistance; that all direct and indirect quotations or borrowings from additional materials and scientific works used during the dissertation writing are accurately and properly cited; confirmation that the candidate has not previously attempted to obtain a doctoral degree and that the submitted dissertation is an original work not defended at another institution of higher education; and a statement regarding the choice between a rigorosum examination or dissertation defense.

The evaluation of the dissertation's quality involves two reviewers, each of whom provides a separate review justifying the acceptance or rejection of the work. If the dissertation is accepted for consideration, it is evaluated according to the following grading system: summa cum laude ("excellent"), 0.5; magna cum laude

(“very good”), 1; cum laude (“good”), 2; rite (“satisfactory”), 3. This grading system also applies to the evaluation of the rigorosum or defense.

The regulations stipulate that professors and associate professors of faculties with the right to conduct examinations should be given the opportunity to review the dissertation and the reviewers’ reports. They are notified in advance of the start date for reviewing the work and reports, as well as the option to submit a written opinion.

If the doctoral candidate opts for a rigorosum, the dean, as the representative of the Chair of the Commission, invites the candidate in writing to the examination and informs them of the examiners. The candidate’s preferences regarding examiners are taken into account but are not binding. Each of the two parts of the rigorosum is conducted by different examiners. Each examiner appoints a co-examiner from their specialization, who must be at least an associate professor or a defended research fellow. The rigorosum in the primary specialization lasts approximately 75 minutes, while the additional discipline and the history of philosophical doctrines each last 45 minutes. During the rigorosum, auditors, master’s students, and doctoral candidates may be present. The final result consists of three equally weighted grades, which together form the overall rigorosum assessment.

If the doctoral candidate chooses a dissertation defense, it typically lasts 90–120 minutes and is public. The candidate presents the main theses of their work in a 15–20-minute report, followed by a discussion and consideration of substantive questions methodologically related to the dissertation topic. The dean, as the representative of the Chair of the Commission, appoints a defense committee, which includes the supervisor, reviewers, and 2–3 other experts, among them specialists representing the primary and additional specializations of the promotion. The committee members must agree on a joint evaluation; if no consensus is reached, the overall result is determined based on the grades proposed by all committee members.

The promotion is successfully completed if the dissertation is accepted for consideration and the doctoral candidate receives at least a “satisfactory” (rite) grade for the defense or each rigorosum subject. The overall examination result is determined by a grade that combines the individual assessments for the dissertation and the oral examination, following this grading scale: up to 0.6 – summa cum laude (“excellent”); 0.61 to 1.50 – magna cum laude (“very good”); 1.51 to 2.50 – cum laude (“satisfactory”); 2.51 to 3.15 – rite (“satisfactory”).

Regulatory documents allow for the dissertation to be published in a periodical, as a monograph, or in electronic form, with the mandatory indication that it was defended at the Ukrainian Free University in Munich. The revised version of the work, incorporating feedback from the supervisor and reviewers, must be approved by them prior to publication.

Broadly speaking, regarding its content, the structure of pedagogical studies includes the following courses:

- A mandatory course, “Methodology of Writing Academic Papers”;
- Profile-specific elective courses (10 courses for master’s students, 7 advanced profile courses for doctoral students), offered within the program (“Philosophy of Education,” “Features of the Development of Pedagogical Theories and Education in European Countries,” “Comparative Pedagogy,” “Strategies for Reforming General Secondary Education in Germany and Ukraine in the Second Half of the 20th Century – Early 21st Century (Comparative Context),” “Integration of Young Migrants and Refugees in German Educational Institutions: Challenges for Pedagogy,” “Social Pedagogy and Social Work in Germany,” “Inclusive Education,” “Pedagogical Conflicts: Causes, Behavioral Strategies, and Resolution,” “School Didactics,” “Pedagogical Technologies,” “Science of Learning: How to Teach Children and Learn Yourself?”);

- Elective courses from other disciplines chosen by students (2 courses for master's students);
- Courses in an additional specialization (4 courses for master's students, 2 courses for doctoral students). Students select an additional specialization from the following options: "Psychology," "History," "Ukrainian Language and Literature," "Art Studies," "Comparative Cultural Studies," "Philosophy";
- Additional program requirements for master's students (writing an individual project, completing an internship, or selecting 1 additional course).

An analysis of the academic, informational, and methodological support for the courses in master's and doctoral pedagogy programs at the Ukrainian Free University (UFU) indicates an international context, with literature available in Ukrainian, English, and German. It also reflects consideration of students' opportunities to independently search for useful and engaging publications, as well as a division of sources into mandatory and elective, similar to Ukrainian disciplinary programs. The recommended reading lists for psycho-pedagogical disciplines feature the scholarly contributions of researchers from the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, including V. Kremen, O. Liashenko, O. Lokshyna, S. Maksymenko, N. Nychkalo, S. Sysoieva, M. Sliusarevskyi, and others.

For instance, the source list for the course "Pedagogical Comparative Studies" (authored by T. Havrylenko) includes the scientific-analytical report by V. Kremen, O. Liashenko, and O. Lokshyna titled *General Secondary Education in Ukraine in the Context of Education in European Countries: Duration and Structure* (2020), the textbook by S. Sysoieva and T. Krystopchuk *Educational Systems of European Union Countries: General Characteristics* (2012), the article by S. Sysoieva "Global Research Infrastructure of Comparative Pedagogy" (2019), and monographs co-authored by O. Lokshyna, such as *Trends in School Education Development in EU*

Countries, the USA, and China (2021) and Transformational Processes in School Education in European Union Countries and the USA (2018), among others. The study of the course “Adult Education” (authored by T. Havrylenko) involves referencing the monograph by N. Nychkalo and I. Prokopenko *Adult Education: Global Trends, Ukrainian Realities, and Prospects* (2020). The curriculum for the course “Fundamentals of General Psychology” (authored by O. Kuzio and L. Didkovska) includes the textbook *General Psychology* edited by S. Maksymenko (2004), while the course “Psychology of Migration (Emigration)” (authored by A. Didkovskyi) features the textbook *Psychology of Migration* by M. Sliusarevskyi and O. Blynova (2013).

The design of course curricula, annotations, and syllabi is characterized by authorial approaches: instructors adhere to general requirements regarding the need to present the relevance, objectives, tasks, learning outcomes, topics, independent student work, assessment methods, and grading policies, while there are no rigid templates dictating format, scope, or sequence of information presentation. Faculty members who simultaneously teach at Ukrainian higher education institutions (e.g., Professors T. Havrylenko, S. Kohut, D. Shulzhenko) introduce contemporary Ukrainian approaches to content presentation at UFU.

Key components of UFU’s human-centered educational environment, which includes teacher training, are its library and archive. The main library collection contains over 600 pedagogical publications, while the archive holds approximately 200, many of which were published in Ukraine. L. Rudnytskyi (2011) notes that this is a true treasure trove for scholars interested in Ukrainian émigré life in Europe during the 20th century, particularly German-Ukrainian relations. Daily updates of relevant information and announcements are prepared for faculty and students worldwide. It is worth noting that, in line with modern educational demands, UFU’s

electronic library is undergoing significant development (Ukrainian Free University, n.d.).

The archive preserves dissertations and master's theses, including those in pedagogy, defended at UFU since 1946 (UFU Archive, Munich, Germany). An analysis of dissertation topics reveals the development of philosophical-educational, historical-pedagogical, comparative-pedagogical, and psycho-pedagogical discourses, such as *The School of the Future* (O. Oryshkevych, 1948), *Behaviorism and Its Critique* (I. Fizer, 1949), *Critical Analysis of the Foundations of the Soviet Educational-Upbringing System* (K. Kokhno, 1950), *Psychology and Pedagogy of Inner Balance* (P. Barvinov, 1950), *Ushynsky as a Pedagogue* (H. Zub, 1954), *Experiments in Family Upbringing in the USSR* (V. Kalynnyk, 1961), *Philosophy of Education in American Culture* (Ch. Sobolevskyi, 1962), *Teaching Slavic Languages (Ukrainian, Russian, and Polish) in American Schools* (A. Samofal, 1968), *Comparison of Foreign Language Teaching Methods in the USA and the Soviet Union After World War II* (D. Polutnyk, 1972), *Comparison of Russian Language Teaching Methodology in the USA and Ukrainian Language Teaching in Canada* (M. Smit, 1972), and *The Influence of Schopenhauer on Pedagogical Trends* (A. Zhyvotenko-Piachkov, 1985).

Pedagogical Studies at UFU in a Subject-Process Perspective

The subject-process perspective of the study focuses on examining approaches to the educational process, its characteristics, the interaction of participants, as well as the forms, methods, and technologies of teacher training. To this end, an analysis of reporting documentation was conducted (specifically, rector's reports for the academic years 2019–2020, 2020–2021, autumn 2022–2023, and the 2022–2023 academic year), teaching experiences were studied through classroom observations, and in-depth interviews were held with participants of the educational process.

According to the reporting data from 2019 to 2023, there was a significant increase in the number of students, by 43.1%, attributed to an effective informational campaign. Quarantine restrictions, prompted by the global pandemic that began in 2020, necessitated a shift to remote learning, as was the case in educational institutions across Ukraine. Under these conditions, a substantial effort was made to reformat the educational process without interruptions, maintaining the full scope of courses, exams, and defenses. Initially, ZOOM was employed as the simplest platform, followed by a transition to Microsoft Teams, a more professional tool designed specifically for online teaching. At UFU (Ukrainian Free University), training sessions and methodological seminars were introduced for instructors to master Teams, prepare materials for remote courses, monitor and evaluate student work, and organize online discussions. UFU staff also conducted individual training sessions for students. During this period, under the leadership of the Head of the Pedagogy Department, S. Kohut, the curricula of pedagogy disciplines were updated (see Table 1).

Being at UFU provided an opportunity to directly engage in the educational process, including attending Professor L. Didkovska's lecture "Theoretical Models

and Empirical Studies of PostTraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)” (4 hours) from the course “Psychological Assistance – Post-Traumatic Stress Disorders,” Professor S. Kohut’s lecture “Assessment of Learning Achievements” (4 hours) from the course “Active Learning Methods,” and participating extensively in P. Hiltes’s seminar classes from the course “Teaching and Upbringing Styles in the Modern School: Challenges Not Only for Didactics” (20 hours).

Participation in the learning process allows for the observation that the engagement of students – both those attending in person and online – is exceptionally high. The interaction between instructors and students can be characterized by key terms such as “friendliness,” “mutual respect,” “subjectivity,” “dialogue,” “personality-developmental space,” “practice-oriented approach,” “free and relaxed atmosphere,” “interactive engagement,” and “teamwork. ” Overall, the learning process is predominantly exploratory in nature, with instructors emphasizing the practical application of information, drawing on students’ experiences, providing relevant examples, posing thought-provoking questions, encouraging discussions, and guiding them tolerantly toward critical thinking, conclusions, and generalizations. At the same time, it should be noted that each class is unique and distinctive, a result of the instructor’s authorship and proactivity, as well as the group synergy with students.

A key advantage of being at UFU was the opportunity to apply the method of interviewing participants in the educational process. In-depth interviews regarding teacher training at UFU were semi-standardized, allowing for a consistent structure to compare responses across participants while also accommodating the unique characteristics of each interviewee (Appendix A). The target group, “participants in the educational process of teacher training at UFU,” included representatives of the administration and leadership, instructors, students, and library and archive staff, totaling 10 individuals (UFU Rector Larysa Didkovska, Head of the Pedagogy

Department Svitlana Kohut, Pedagogy Department instructors Dina Shulzhenko and Peter Hiltes, Head of the Library and UFU graduate Ivan Zarytskyi, archivist and UFU student Yuliia Chernomor, project manager and UFU graduate Liliia Bondarenko, academic and student affairs officer and UFU graduate Roman Tiutenko, Master's student in pedagogy Anna Higl, and doctoral student in psychology Viktoriia Danylevska, who is pursuing pedagogy as a second specialization). For each respondent, an individualized guide was prepared, incorporating common questions about methodology, educational management, content, methods, forms, and technologies of teaching, as well as quality assurance, while also accounting for their unique involvement with UFU. Consideration was also given to the fact that some participants fulfill multiple roles, such as being simultaneously administrators and instructors, graduates and staff, or staff and students. Table 1 presents the results of a content analysis of the characteristics of the educational process for teacher training at UFU.

Table 1.

Results of the Content Analysis of Key Features of Teacher Training at UVU Through the Perspective of Educational Process Participants

Parameters	Characteristics
Goals	<p>The training of educators capable of effectively working in a modern educational environment, responding to current challenges – particularly those caused by the full-scale war in Ukraine and the demands of inclusive education – while providing psychosocial support and ensuring quality education under various conditions. This involves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of professional competencies (ensuring deep knowledge and practical skills necessary for effective pedagogical activities); • Cultivation of critical thinking and innovation skills (promoting the ability to analyze, evaluate, and implement innovative methods and technologies in the educational process); • Preparation for work in a multicultural environment (developing skills for interacting with representatives of diverse cultures and adapting to various educational contexts); • Support for psychosocial well-being (training in methods to work with students who have experienced traumatic events and creating a safe, supportive learning environment).
Methodological Approaches	<p>Synergetic: Openness of education, spontaneity, flexibility, innovative learning, recognition of students’ individual needs and capabilities, and nondirective management of the educational process.</p> <p>Competency-Based: Development of educators’ abilities to address professional pedagogical tasks through acquired values, attitudes, professional knowledge, skills, and professionally significant personal qualities.</p> <p>Environmental: Indirect management of the educational process with a primary focus on the proactivity of the learner, fostering self-learning, selfeducation, and professional self-development.</p> <p>Person-Centered: Development of individual abilities, creative potential, and professional competencies of future educators, taking into account their personal needs, values, and motivations.</p> <p>Personological: Engagement of experienced, highly professional, and talented scholars with strong reputations in teaching; creation of conditions and support for instructors’ professional autonomy; influence of their original approaches, individual teaching styles, pedagogical experience, and the scientific legacy of prominent figures in the institution’s history (e.g., for UVU – I. Mirchuk, A. Voloshyn, H. Vashchenko, and others) on the formation and development of future teachers’ professional agency.</p>

	<p>Andragogical: Focus on adult education, considering learners' life experiences, motivation for self-development, and need for practical application of knowledge.</p> <p>Interdisciplinary: Integration of knowledge from various academic fields such as pedagogy, psychology, history, sociology, cultural studies, Ukrainian studies, etc., to form a comprehensive understanding of the educational process and enhance the agency of future teachers.</p> <p>Social-Constructivist: Active interaction with the social environment and collaborative activities, emphasizing cooperation, discussion, reflection, and joint problem-solving to foster critical thinking and professional competence in future educators.</p> <p>Trauma-Informed: Development of competencies in future teachers to understand the impact of psychological trauma on students' emotional states, behavior, and learning abilities; fostering empathy, supporting mental health, addressing the individual needs of students who have experienced stress or trauma, and creating a safe and supportive educational environment.</p>
Teacher's Role	A facilitator, mentor, moderator, and consultant who creates conditions for students' independent learning and development, supports and motivates them, fosters personal growth, assists in solving educational and practical tasks, and employs a democratic teaching style.
Student's Role	An active and proactive participant in the educational process, taking responsibility for their own learning and development, independently seeking, analyzing, and critically evaluating information, collaborating with instructors and peers to address tasks, and reflecting on their own learning experiences and outcomes.
Interaction Between Teachers and Students, and Among Students	Subject-to-subject, partnership-based relationships with well-established communication facilitated by modern management tools and social platforms. A distinctive feature is the absence of fixed study groups, which does not hinder effective communication, further supported by a designated academic and student affairs coordinator. The university involves students in various events and organizes informal gatherings.
Learning Motivation	Creation of a supportive educational environment that considers students' individual needs and interests, ensures respect, encourages achievements, and fosters open communication. Motivational factors include: Professional development: Students aspire to gain quality education that enhances career growth and professional fulfillment; Cognitive interest: The desire to deepen understanding of their chosen field and acquire new knowledge stimulates active participation in the learning process; Self-affirmation: Students seek to demonstrate their abilities and achievements, boosting their self-confidence; Social interaction: University education provides opportunities to build new connections, exchange experiences, and expand professional networks.
Organization of the Educational Process	A blended format combining online and offline learning; a flexible system allowing students to create their own schedules by selecting courses from a proposed list in line with program requirements; diverse forms of class delivery; prioritization of creative, productive tasks; provision of conditions

	for individual and group educational projects; use of active learning methods; variety in task selection; and opportunities for participation in research and practical events, including annual student academic conferences.
Internal Quality Assurance in Education	Monitoring the needs and demands of applicants based on the analysis of motivation letters, with results informing updates to educational content (e.g., introduction of courses such as “Transformational Pedagogy (Pedagogy of Change),” “Adult Education,” and “Trauma Pedagogy”); continuous improvement of curricula and programs with rapid responses to contemporary challenges; engagement of leading experts with international experience in teaching; ongoing professional development for instructors; adherence to Study Regulations for monitoring and assessing academic achievements; operation of a system to prevent and detect academic plagiarism; provision of necessary resources for the educational process; and development of information systems for effective management, methodological support, and transparency of UFU activities.
Social and Humanitarian Activities	Involvement of teachers and students in volunteer projects, community initiatives, and cultural-educational events.
Support for Graduate Employment	Conducting career training, coaching, and providing information on job opportunities. Engaging talented graduates in work at UFU serves as an example of effective personnel policy.
Uniqueness of UVU Pedagogical Studies	Preservation of pedagogical traditions established by distinguished UFU instructors who laid the foundations of Ukrainian pedagogy rooted in national values and Christian ethics, combined with support for innovations by modern instructors who create a space for transformational pedagogy. This fosters the agency of future educators, their self-reliance, creativity, social responsibility, and professional autonomy. The training focuses on inclusive education and psychological-pedagogical support for working with children who have experienced trauma, particularly in wartime conditions. Opportunities to acquire an additional specialization enhance interdisciplinarity and multifaceted learning. A sense of community preserves Ukrainian identity and culture, providing students with a “sense of home.” Multiculturalism is both a feature of the educational environment and an integral part of teacher training content.

A separate focus in the interview was given to the digitization of education and its impact on the quality of teacher training, which enabled the conduction of a corresponding SWOT analysis (Table 2).

Table 2.

SWOT Analysis of Teacher Training in the Context of Digitization

<p>Strengs – Advantages, Positive Aspects</p>	<p>Weaknesses – Challenges, Disadvantages</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the continuity of the educational process during the COVID19 pandemic, war, and other crisis situations; • Opportunities for remote access for instructors and students; • Implementation of blended learning possibilities; • Provision of individualized learning; • Continuous open access to educational and methodological resources; • Development and enhancement of digital competence among learners; • Promotion of inclusivity, ensuring access to education for individuals with disabilities and those in remote regions; • Greater opportunities for career guidance activities; • Increased efficiency in managing the educational process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital divides (between instructors, between students, and between instructors and students); • Overburdening of instructors; • Unstable internet connectivity; • Lack of face-to-face interaction, leading to a reduced level of emotional connection between instructors and students; • Fatigue, psychological discomfort, and isolation of participants in the educational process.
<p>Opportunities – Prospects, Reserves, Solutions for Future Challenges</p>	<p>Threats – Risks, Dangers, Potential Future Challenges</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a safe and comfortable digital educational environment; • Continuous professional development of instructors in the field of digital technologies; • Ensuring adherence to the principles and rules of academic integrity, including plagiarism checks for master’s theses and dissertations, and written confirmation of independent work by graduates; • Training learners to use artificial intelligence (AI) as a tool for environmentally responsible information handling; • Implementation of modern interactive pedagogical technologies, such as gamification and augmented reality; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyberattacks and information leaks; • Insufficient level of digital security; • Decreased student motivation and poorer assimilation of material; • Misuse of AI by students in completing assignments and writing papers; • Difficulty in monitoring students’ independent completion of tasks in an online environment; • Decline in students’ critical thinking and creativity; • Predominance of globalized content, posing a risk of losing national identity.

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|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formative assessment of students' academic achievements, focusing not only on final outcomes but also on the process of achieving them; • Achieving a balance between online and offline learning; • Introduction of modern online platforms, such as "Knowledge Academy" for UFU (Ukrainian Virtual University). | |
|---|--|

Since 9 of the interviewees have experience obtaining higher education in Ukraine, 3 of them teach at Ukrainian higher education institutions (HEIs), and one participant is an expert on Ukrainian education, their opinions on the similarities and differences between studying at Ukrainian institutions and the Ukrainian Free University (UFU) are considered significant. Thus, the following common features have been identified: adherence to the requirements of the Bologna education system, the application of a competencybased approach, a blended learning format, a general orientation toward the use of innovative pedagogical technologies, the digitalization of education, and measures for internal quality assurance in education. Key distinctions of the UFU include a high level of academic freedom; rapid response to external challenges and the demands of learners; a preference for unconventional forms and methods of teaching; a flexible, individualized learning trajectory for students; an emphasis on creativity and innovation in independent work; greater autonomy for learners, described as "greater freedom and greater responsibility"; the absence of fixed study groups; openness of instructors to communication and their support; psychological comfort; high variability in the choice of academic disciplines; the opportunity to obtain a second specialization; and a different procedure for the preparation and defense of doctoral dissertations in philosophy.

Recommendations for Ukrainian Higher Pedagogical Institutions on Implementing the Positive Experience of Developing Teacher Agency at UFU

The research findings have enabled the formulation of the following recommendations for Ukrainian higher pedagogical education institutions regarding the implementation of positive experiences from the UFU in fostering the agency of educators (Romanova, 2025a, p. 18; Romanova, 2025c, p. 5–7):

- Strengthen collaboration with European, particularly German, HEIs and research institutions to exchange experiences, publications, conduct scientific and practical events, and promote academic mobility for learners and instructors in the context of teacher training;
- Combine pedagogical traditions with innovations, leveraging the history of the HEI, while supporting and encouraging progressive instructors who are respected and recognized by students and colleagues and demonstrate high professional activity;
- Provide greater academic freedom for instructors in selecting teaching methods and approaches to assessment;
- Ensure rapid updates to the content of academic disciplines, flexibility in curricula and programs based on monitoring the needs and demands of applicants;
- Prevent the duplication of course content both at the level of higher education programs and with school subjects;
- Implement courses on pedagogical ethics, the formation and development of teachers' professional subjectivity based on Ukrainian pedagogical tradition;
- Ensure continuous and systematic preparation of future educators for fostering national identity in children;

- Prepare educators for work in a multicultural environment to develop skills for interacting with representatives of different cultures and adapting to diverse educational contexts;
- Ensure transparent and genuine choice of academic courses for students;
- Enhance the comparative context of foreign pedagogical experience, especially European, in course content and support relevant scientific research by students;
- Integrate psychological and pedagogical support for students experiencing stress or trauma due to war conditions and post-war recovery into teacher preparation;
- Ensure an interdisciplinary approach in teacher preparation for creating an inclusive environment by developing programs that combine contemporary positive practices from pedagogy, psychology, and social work, including studying the experience of working with Ukrainian migrant and refugee children in European countries, particularly in Germany;
- Develop future teachers' readiness to implement transformative pedagogy for deep learning and the development of critical thinking in students;
- Provide opportunities for students to obtain a second specialization in related fields, which will enhance the interdisciplinarity of teacher preparation and increase graduates' competitiveness in the labor market;
- Implement modern scientific, informational, and methodological resources into the educational process, promoting the achievements of domestic and foreign pedagogical science;
- Systematically and continuously apply the potential of university libraries and archives in the preparation of educators.

Publication and dissemination of project results

The results of the project were published in both English and Ukrainian in the article “Analysis of Pedagogical Studies at the Ukrainian Free University in Germany” in the journal “Professional Pedagogics” (ISSN 2707-3092; <https://jrnl.ivet.edu.ua/index.php/1>):

Romanova, G. (2025a). *Analysis of pedagogical studies at the Ukrainian Free University in Germany*. *Professional Pedagogics*, 1(30), 3–24. <https://doi.org/10.32835/2707-3092.2025.30.3-24>

The scientific publication is included in the “List of Scientific Professional Publications of Ukraine” (Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine dated January 15, 2018, No. 32, registered by the Ministry of Justice of Ukraine on February 6, 2018, under No. 148/21600); it is indexed in the scientometric databases Index Copernicus International (since 12.07.2018), Matrix for the Analysis of Journals (since 01.02.2021); and in the databases CrossRef (ISSN 2707-3092, 2223-5752) (since 22.11.2018), Ulrich’s Periodicals Directory (since 25.08.2014), ERIH PLUS (since 20.01.2020), and the search engine Google Scholar (since 25.08.2014); also included in Academic Resource Index: ResearchBib (since 01.01.2019), WorldCat, and the Education Resources Information Center (ERIC); and is presented in the ranking of Bibliometrics of Ukrainian Science (since 01.01.2019).

The article is available in the Electronic Library of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine: <https://lib.iitta.gov.ua/id/eprint/745036/>

Information about the main results of the project was also published in Ukrainian in the article “Results of the Project “Analysis of Pedagogical Studies at the Ukrainian Free University in Germany” within the DAAD Program “Future Ukraine: Research grants for Ukrainian Master’s students and researchers” in the

journal “Herald of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine” (ISSN Online 2707-305X; <https://visnyk.naps.gov.ua/index.php/journal>):

Romanova, G. M. (2025c). Results of the Project “Analysis of Pedagogical Studies at the Ukrainian Free University in Germany” within the DAAD Programme “Future Ukraine: Research grants for Ukrainian Master’s students and researchers”. *Herald of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine*, 7(1), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.37472/v.naes.2025.7107>

The Herald of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine is indexed in the following databases, registries, and search systems: [Crossref](#), [Index Copernicus International](#), Open Ukrainian Citation Index (OUCI), [Dimensions](#), [Unpaywall](#), Directory of Open Access Scholarly Resources (ROAD), [OCLC WorldCat](#), and [Google Scholar](#). The website of the Herald of the NAES of Ukraine uses the [LOCKSS](#) system for distributed archival storage of published content in numerous libraries and information centers. The LOCKSS participating libraries ensure long-term preservation of complete journal archives and automatic recovery of any damaged information.

The information about the article was shared through the journal's Facebook page: https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=2574172746117783&id=10005752481745&rdid=h7hF6akaC1myrkjJ#

The article is available in the Electronic Library of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine: <https://surl.li/ghqtns>

An interview with the Rector of the Ukrainian Free University, Prof. Larysa Didkovska, was published with her consent in the open repository Zenodo:

Romanova, G. (2025b). Features of pedagogical studies at the Ukrainian Free University [Interview with the Rector of UFU, Professor Larysa Didkovska]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15175485>

The interview is also available in the Electronic Library of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine: <https://surl.li/apnqvm>; <https://surl.li/qwakic>

Information about the progress of the project was regularly shared on the social network Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/anna.romanova.7564>). In particular, nine posts were published:

Romanova, G. [Anna Romanova]. (2025, February 1). *On the start of work on the project at the Ukrainian Free University (UFU) in Munich, Germany under the DAAD Germany programme* [Facebook status update with photo]. Facebook. https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=2512730415595350&id=100005752481745

Romanova, G. [Anna Romanova]. (2025, February 7). *On the results of the first week of work* [Facebook status update with photo]. Facebook. https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=2518087281726330&id=100005752481745

Romanova, G. [Anna Romanova]. (2025, February 14). *On the results of the second week of work* [Facebook status update with photo]. Facebook. https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=2523926004475791&id=100005752481745

Romanova, G. [Anna Romanova]. (2025, February 21). *On the results of the third week of work* [Facebook status update with photo]. Facebook. https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=2530316277170097&id=100005752481745

Romanova, G. [Anna Romanova]. (2025, February 24). *On joining UFU colleagues in rallies supporting Ukraine on the third anniversary of Russia's full-scale invasion in Munich* [Facebook status update with photo]. Facebook.

https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=2533604323507959&id=100005752481745

Romanova, G. [Anna Romanova]. (2025, February 25). *On participating in a UFU commemorative event in Munich on the 3rd anniversary of the beginning of Russia's full-scale war against Ukraine* [Facebook status update with photo]. Facebook. https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=2537349739800084&id=100005752481745

Romanova, G. [Anna Romanova]. (2025, March 1). *On the completion of stay at the Ukrainian Free University (UFU) under the DAAD Germany programme* [Facebook status update with photo]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1Hc4AgaeCF/>

Romanova, G. [Anna Romanova]. (2025, April 05). *On the publication of the article "Analysis of Pedagogical Studies of the Ukrainian Free University in Germany" based on the results of the project within the DAAD programme "Ukraine of the Future: Research Grants for Ukrainian Master's Students and Researchers"* [Facebook status update with photo]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1ByyNFgjCN/>

Romanova, G. [Anna Romanova]. (2025, April 09). *About the publication of an interview with the Rector of UFU, Prof. Larysa Didkovska "Features of pedagogical studies at the Ukrainian Free University"* [Facebook status update with photo]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/18pttXLLhV/>

At the Academic Council of the Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, the information was heard from the leading researcher of the Department of Foreign Systems of Vocational Education, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor Ganna Romanova, regarding the results of the project "Analysis of Pedagogical Studies of the Ukrainian Free

University in Germany” under the DAAD programme “The Future of Ukraine: Research Grants for Ukrainian Master's Students and Researchers.”

The Academic Council approved a decision to support the dissemination of the project results during the scientific and practical events of the IVE of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, to ensure systemic cooperation within the framework of the signed agreement with the Ukrainian Free University (Munich, Germany), and to activate the international mobility of scientific staff of the IPE of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine (Appendix B).

On March 27, 2025, as part of the 19th All-Ukrainian Scientific and Practical (Reporting) Conference “Development of Vocational Education in the Context of War, Post-War Recovery, and European Integration of Ukraine” (held online on March 27–28, 2025), organized by the Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, a presentation was delivered on the topic: “Experience of Internal Quality Assurance in Education at the Ukrainian Free University (based on the results of the project “Analysis of Pedagogical Studies at the Ukrainian Free University in Germany”).” (National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine & Institute of Vocational Education, 2025).

To further disseminate the results of the project, participation is planned in scientific and practical events, including:

- the Scientific Conference “The Ukrainian Free University: Traditions and Prominent Figures”, dedicated to the 80th anniversary of UFU’s activity in Germany, to be held on May 21–22, 2025 at the Ukrainian Free University (presentation title: “The Formation and Development of Pedagogical Studies at the Ukrainian Free University”);
- the 31st International Scientific and Practical Online Conference “Competence-Based Principles of Professional Training in the Context of Global and

National Experience: Current Challenges and Prospects”, which will take place on May 22–23, 2025, at Ivan Franko Zhytomyr State University (presentation title: “Transformational Pedagogy of the Ukrainian Free University: History and Modernity”).

A project page was created on the website of the Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine (Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, n.d.).

Establishing international cooperation

An important outcome of the project implementation was the signing of an Agreement on International Cooperation between the Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, represented by its Director, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, and Full Member of the NAES of Ukraine Valentyna Radkevych, and the Ukrainian Free University (Germany), represented by its Rector, Prof. Dr. Larysa Didkovska (Appendix C). The agreement aims to consolidate efforts to promote European principles of educational systems' functioning in Ukraine, introduce European scholars to the national characteristics of the Ukrainian education system, and develop joint approaches to ensuring the socio-humanitarian development of future professionals as representatives of the free democratic world (Institute of Vocational Education, 2025; National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, 2025).

During the online meeting held on February 19, 2025, concrete steps for implementing the areas of cooperation defined in the Agreement were discussed. In particular, these included the development and implementation of joint projects and/or programs, the conduct of collaborative research aimed at promoting European values and Ukrainian educational and cultural traditions, the organization of joint scientific and practical events, mutual support in fostering academic mobility of researchers and students, engagement of scholars and academic staff in publishing in institutional periodicals, enhancement of scientific cooperation among editorial board members of institutional journals, improvement of the quality of PhD training within educational and research programs, and the promotion and dissemination of the activities of the cooperating institutions.

Conclusions

The Ukrainian Free University (UFU) stands as a unique institution of higher education that integrates Ukrainian pedagogical traditions with European standards. Its historical journey underscores the significance of preserving academic freedom and national identity amidst emigration. Prominent figures such as Ivan Mirchuk, Avgustyn Voloshyn, Hryhoriy Vashchenko, and others laid the foundation for the development of pedagogical studies oriented toward humanistic values and the formation of the Ukrainian educational ideal.

The training of educators at UFU addresses contemporary challenges, including inclusive education, the education of migrant and refugee children, and modern approaches to teaching in schools and extracurricular educational institutions. The content of pedagogical studies includes a mandatory course, “Methodology of Writing Scientific Papers”; profile-specific elective courses (10 courses for master’s students and 7 advanced profile courses for doctoral students), offered within the program (“Philosophy of Education,” “Features of the Development of Pedagogical Theories and Education in European Countries,” “Comparative Pedagogy,” “Strategies for Reforming General Secondary Education in Germany and Ukraine in the Second Half of the 20th Century to the Early 21st Century (Comparative Context),” “Integration of Young Migrants and Refugees in German Educational Institutions: Challenges for Pedagogy,” “Social Pedagogy and Social Work in Germany,” “Inclusive Education,” “Pedagogical Conflicts: Causes, Behavioral Strategies, and Resolution,” “Didactics of School Education,” “Pedagogical Technologies,” “Learning Science: How to Teach Children and Learn Yourself?”); elective courses from other disciplines chosen by students (2 courses for master’s students); courses in an additional specialization (4 courses for master’s students, 2 courses for doctoral students); and additional program requirements for

master's students (writing an individual project, completing an internship, or selecting one additional course).

Distinctive features of the scientific component of the studies include the freedom of master's and doctoral students to choose their research topic and supervisor; consideration of their preferences regarding the composition of the examination committee; an emphasis on comparative context in research; quantitative evaluation of both master's theses and dissertations, with the involvement of the academic supervisor in the assessment process; the option for doctoral students to select the form of their promotion (rigorosum or defense); the absence of requirements for publications or preliminary validation of results, with the possibility of publishing the work post-defense provided it references the institution of defense and is approved by the supervisor and reviewers after revisions.

An analysis of the scientific-informational and educational-methodological support for the master's and doctoral pedagogy programs at UFU confirms its international context, with literature available in Ukrainian, English, and German, and consideration of students' opportunities to independently seek useful and relevant publications. Similar to Ukrainian programs, sources are divided into mandatory and elective categories. The inclusion of works by scholars from the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine in the recommended reading lists for psycho-pedagogical disciplines demonstrates attention to the results of contemporary Ukrainian educational research. The design of course curricula, annotations, and syllabi reflects authorial approaches.

Key components of UFU's human-centered educational environment, which encompasses teacher training, include its library and archive, which provide daily information services to faculty and students worldwide, as well as a functioning electronic library. An analysis of dissertation topics stored in the archive highlights

the development of philosophical-educational, historical-pedagogical, comparative-pedagogical, and psycho-pedagogical discourses.

A study of the specifics of the educational process for training educators reveals high levels of student engagement in classes, a predominant focus on exploratory learning, and instructors' emphasis on the practical application of information. Faculty draw on students' experiences, provide relevant examples, pose problem-based questions, encourage discussions, and guide them toward critical thinking, conclusions, and generalizations in a tolerant manner.

Content analysis of interviews with participants in the educational process has enabled the clarification of learning objectives in light of modern challenges; the identification of methodological approaches to teacher training (synergetic, competency-based, environmental, personality-oriented, personological, andragogical, interdisciplinary, socio-constructivist, trauma-informed); and the characterization of: the instructor's roles (facilitator, mentor, moderator, consultant), the student's role (an active and proactive participant in the educational process), the nature of their interaction (subject-to-subject, partnership-based), learning motivation (creating a supportive educational environment that accounts for individual needs and interests), and the organization of the educational process (flexible system, blended learning, variability in independent work, interactivity, project-based learning). Internal quality assurance in education includes monitoring the needs and demands of applicants and incorporating the findings; continuously improving curricula and programs; promptly addressing contemporary challenges; engaging leading experts with international experience in teaching; fostering ongoing professional development for faculty; adhering to Study Regulations regarding the monitoring and evaluation of academic achievements; and maintaining a system to prevent and detect academic plagiarism. Sociohumanitarian activities involve faculty and student participation in volunteer projects, community

initiatives, and cultural-educational events, while career support for graduates includes career training, coaching, information on employment opportunities, and the recruitment of talented alumni to work at UFU.

These findings affirm UFU's uniqueness in preserving pedagogical traditions established by its distinguished faculty while supporting innovations by contemporary instructors, creating a space for transformative pedagogy; focusing training on inclusive education and psycho-pedagogical support for children with traumatic experiences, particularly in wartime conditions; offering additional specializations that promote interdisciplinarity and multidimensional learning; fostering a sense of community that preserves Ukrainian identity and culture, providing students with a "sense of home"; and embracing multiculturalism.

Based on a SWOT analysis, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of teacher training in the context of digitalization were identified. We emphasize the following ways to address problems in the future: creating a safe and comfortable digital educational environment; continuous professional development of teachers in the field of digital technologies; ensuring compliance with the principles and rules of academic integrity; teaching students to use AI as a tool for ecological work with information; implementing modern interactive pedagogical technologies, including gamification, augmented reality; formative assessment of students' learning achievements; balance between online and offline learning; and the introduction of modern online platforms.

The results of the DAAD-funded research project "Analysis of Pedagogical Studies at the Ukrainian Free University" demonstrate the development of self-reliant educators capable of supporting national identity, critical thinking, implementing innovative approaches, and working in a multicultural environment, which confirms the significance of UFU's experience for the development of

Ukrainian pedagogy in the face of global challenges and European integration, as reflected in the formulated recommendations.

An important outcome of the project was the signing of an Agreement on International Cooperation between the Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine and the Ukrainian Free University (Germany), aimed at consolidating efforts to promote European principles of education system functioning in Ukraine, familiarize European scholars with the national peculiarities of the Ukrainian education system, and develop joint approaches to ensuring the socio-humanitarian development of future professionals as representatives of a free democratic world. Specific steps for the development of cooperation were outlined, including the development and implementation of joint projects and/or programs, conducting joint research aimed at promoting European values and Ukrainian educational and cultural traditions, organizing joint scientific and practical events, mutual assistance in the development of academic mobility of scientists and students, involving scientists and academic staff in publications in periodicals of institutions, strengthening scientific cooperation among members of the editorial boards of periodicals of institutions, improving the quality of PhD training under educational and scientific programs, and highlighting and promoting the activities of cooperation entities.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Guides for In-Depth Interviews with Participants of the Teacher Training Educational Process at UFU

Interview Topic – Features of the Pedagogical Studies at UFU.

Objective – To explore participants' perceptions of the teaching and learning characteristics in teacher training at UFU.

Duration – One hour.

Opening Remarks

Dear _____,

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview on the perceptions of educational process participants regarding the features of teaching and learning in teacher training at the Ukrainian Free University (UFU). This interview is conducted as part of the research project “Analysis of Pedagogical Studies at the Ukrainian Free University in Germany” under the DAAD Programme “Ukraine of the Future: Research Grants for Ukrainian Master's Students and Researchers.”

I am Ganna Romanova, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, and Leading Researcher at the Department of Foreign Systems of Vocational Education of the Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine. I am the author of this project. Your opinion is extremely important to me, and there are no right or wrong answers. Please respond clearly and concisely, and feel free to ask for clarifications if needed.

Appendix A1

Interview Guide with the Rector of UFU, Larysa Didkovska

1. What is your personal history of teaching and management at UFU? How did you come to the university?
2. What management principles have you implemented as the Dean of the Faculty of Philosophy and now as the Rector?
3. Which psychological and pedagogical disciplines have you developed and currently teach, including those for future educators?
4. What ideas for updating teacher training programs have you successfully implemented?
5. How is the focus on preparing teachers for children of Ukrainian refugees being realized?
6. What is the role of teacher preparation for inclusive education?
7. What is the main focus of students' research work? What topics do students choose for their master's theses and dissertations?
8. What is your vision of the socio-humanitarian and psychological-pedagogical components of teacher training at UFU?
9. What do you know about the employment and career paths of UFU graduates?
10. How would you describe faculty collaboration in developing training programs?
11. What are the main requirements for the academic staff? Is the involvement of guest professors and associate professors a part of the university's policy?

12. Which teaching methods and technologies do you prefer and actively use?
13. What advantages and disadvantages do you see in blended and distance learning?
14. How is digitalization implemented in the educational process? Is AI being used?
15. How would you characterize your teaching style?
16. What do you consider essential for ensuring the quality of education at UFU? What indicators, in your opinion, determine a future teacher's readiness to teach?
17. What role does the Pedagogical Institute play in UFU's activities? Is the university currently a center for professional development and internships for educators in and from Ukraine?
18. How is the professional development of UFU faculty members carried out?
19. How do traditions and innovations coexist at UFU? Which traditions remain constant?
20. Which university figures have significantly influenced the goals and values of teacher training?
21. Why do students in all study programs obtain a second specialty? You teach students who are pursuing a teaching specialty as their second major. What requirements do you see for the psychological component of teacher training? How can a trauma-informed approach be implemented in teaching?
22. Are there connections with vocational education institutions in Bavaria? Do your graduates work there?
23. How are students trained to participate in volunteer activities?
24. How is an individualized learning trajectory ensured for students?
25. What is your vision for the future development of UFU, and what role does teacher training play in this process?
26. What key words would you use to describe the uniqueness of teacher training at UFU?
27. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the adoption of UFU's teacher training experience could be beneficial?

Appendix A2
Interview Guide with the Head of the Department of Pedagogy at UFU,
Professor Svitlana Kohut

1. What is your personal history of teaching at UFU? How did you come to the university?
2. Which pedagogical disciplines have you developed and teach?
3. What ideas for updating teacher education programs have you been able to implement?
4. How is the focus on training teachers for children of Ukrainian refugees being realized?
5. How is the preparation for inclusive education carried out?
6. What is the main focus of students' scientific work? What topics do graduate students choose for their master's theses and dissertations?
7. How is the socio-humanitarian and psychological-pedagogical training conducted?
8. What do you know about the employment and career paths of graduates?
9. How would you characterize the interaction between faculty in the development of teacher preparation programs?
10. What are the main requirements for the academic and teaching staff? Is the involvement of invited professors and associate professors a part of the university's policy?
11. What teaching methods and technologies do you prefer and willingly apply?
12. What are the advantages and disadvantages of blended and distance learning?
13. How is digitalization implemented in the educational process? Is AI applied?
14. How would you describe your teaching style?
15. What do you consider the key elements in ensuring the quality of education at UFU? What, personally, are the indicators of a future teacher's readiness to teach?
16. How is the professional development of the pedagogy department's faculty conducted?
17. How do traditions and innovations align? Which traditions remain constant?
18. Which prominent scholars from UFU have significantly influenced the goals and values of teacher preparation?
19. Do you teach students who are obtaining a teaching degree as a second degree? Are there connections with vocational education in terms of training teachers for vocational education institutions?
20. How is student preparation for volunteer activities organized?
21. How is the individual learning trajectory of students ensured?
22. What is your prognostic vision for the development of the Department of Pedagogy at UFU?
23. What key words would you use to characterize the uniqueness of teacher preparation at UFU?
24. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the experience of teacher preparation at UFU could be useful?

Appendix A3
Interview Guide with the Lecturer of the Department of Pedagogy at the UFU,
Professor Dina Shulzhenko

1. What is your personal history of teaching at UFU? How did you come to the university?
2. Which pedagogical disciplines have you developed and teach?
3. What ideas for updating the teacher preparation program have you been able to implement?
4. How is the focus on training teachers for children of Ukrainian refugees being realized?
5. How is the preparation for inclusive education carried out? What are the specifics of teaching the "Inclusive Education" course?
6. What is the main focus of students' scientific work? What topics do graduate students choose for their master's theses and dissertations?
7. How is the socio-humanitarian and psychological-pedagogical training conducted?
8. What do you know about the employment and career paths of graduates?
9. How would you characterize the interaction between faculty in the development of teacher preparation programs?
10. What are the main requirements for the teaching staff?
11. What teaching methods and technologies do you prefer and willingly apply?
12. What are the advantages and disadvantages of blended and distance learning?
13. How would you describe your teaching style?
14. What do you consider the indicators of a future teacher's readiness to teach?
15. How is the professional development of the pedagogy department's faculty conducted?
16. How do traditions and innovations align? Which traditions remain constant?
17. Which prominent scholars from UFU have significantly influenced the goals and values of teacher preparation?
18. Do you teach students who are obtaining a teaching degree as a second degree? Are there connections with vocational education in terms of training teachers for vocational education institutions?
19. How is student preparation for volunteer activities organized?
20. What key words would you use to characterize the uniqueness of teacher preparation at UFU?
21. How is the individual learning trajectory of students ensured?
22. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the experience of teacher preparation, especially for inclusive education, at UFU could be useful?

Appendix A4

Interview Guide with the Lecturer of the Department of Pedagogy at UFU, Peter Hilkes

1. What is your personal history of teaching at UFU? How did you come to the university?
2. Which pedagogical disciplines have you developed and teach?
3. What ideas for updating the teacher preparation program have you been able to implement?
4. How is the focus on training teachers for children of Ukrainian refugees being realized?
5. How is the preparation for inclusive education carried out?
6. What is the main focus of students' scientific work? What topics do graduate students choose for their master's theses and dissertations?
7. How is the socio-humanitarian and psychological-pedagogical training conducted?
8. What do you know about the employment and career paths of graduates?
9. How would you characterize the interaction between faculty in the development of teacher preparation programs?
10. What are the main requirements for the teaching staff?
11. What teaching methods and technologies do you prefer and willingly apply?
12. What are the advantages and disadvantages of blended and distance learning?
13. How would you describe your teaching style?
14. What do you consider the indicators of a future teacher's readiness to teach?
15. How is the professional development of the pedagogy department's faculty conducted?
16. How do traditions and innovations align? Which traditions remain constant?
17. Which prominent scholars from UFU have significantly influenced the goals and values of teacher preparation?
18. Do you teach students who are obtaining a teaching degree as a second degree? Are there connections with vocational education in terms of training teachers for vocational education institutions?
19. How is student preparation for volunteer activities organized?
20. What key words would you use to characterize the uniqueness of teacher preparation at UFU?
21. How is the individual learning trajectory of students ensured?
22. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the experience of teacher preparation at UFU could be useful?

Appendix A5
Interview Guide with the Teaching and Learning Officer and UFU Graduate Dr. Roman Tyutenko

1. What is your personal history of studying and working at UFU? What was your previous education? If you studied in Ukraine, what are the similarities and differences between studying at UFU and Ukrainian universities?
2. How were the classes at UFU? What motivated you to study? What teaching methods and forms of work did you enjoy?
3. Which subjects do you remember the most?
4. Did you study subjects related to the socio-humanitarian curriculum?
5. Did you choose courses in psychology and pedagogy? If so, how did they enrich you, and what new knowledge and skills did you gain?
6. What is your experience of participating in educational projects?
7. What topic did you work on for your dissertation?
8. What are the main requirements for a dissertation and its defense? How would you characterize the role of your scientific advisor in your preparation?
9. Did you participate in scientific conferences?
10. Did you have any publications before and after defending your dissertation?
11. What normative documents define the requirements for educational programs for Master's and future PhD students in Pedagogy? How are the standards of Bavarian higher pedagogical education considered, and is the Ukrainian experience still relevant?
12. What are the main requirements for the educational programs for Master's and future PhD students in Pedagogy?
13. What are the main requirements for the programs of educational disciplines (courses)? Do you use syllabi for students?
14. Where is the information about the educational and methodological support for the disciplines located?
15. What is the overall student body at UFU, and how many are studying the "Pedagogy" specialty in the Master's program, and how many in the PhD preparation program?
16. How many students are obtaining a teaching degree as a second degree (by faculty)? Is there still a practice of training teachers for trade schools among students of the Faculty of State and Economic Sciences? Are there connections with vocational education?
17. Do you collect information about the employment and career paths of graduates? What are the main employment trends for graduates with a teaching specialty?
18. How is the educational work with students organized? What are its main directions? What is the foundation of successful volunteer activities for students?
19. What key words would you use to characterize the uniqueness of teacher preparation at UFU?
20. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the experience of teacher preparation at UFU could be useful?

Appendix A6

Interview Guide with the Project Manager and UFU Graduate, Dr. Lilia Bondarenko

1. What is your personal history of studying and working at UFU? What was your previous education?
2. How were the classes at UFU? What motivated you to study? What forms of work did you enjoy?
3. Which subjects do you remember the most?
4. Did you study subjects related to the socio-humanitarian curriculum?
5. Did you choose courses in psychology and pedagogy? If so, how did they enrich you, and what new knowledge and skills did you gain?
6. What is your experience of participating in educational projects?
7. What topic did you choose for your Master's thesis? What are the main requirements for it? How is the thesis writing progressing?
8. Did you participate in scientific conferences?
9. Do you have experience with publications?
10. How is the individual learning trajectory of students ensured?
11. What do you think is the role of the lecturer in modern student education? Which classes became the most significant for you?
12. What is the role of digitalization in modern student education? Have you used artificial intelligence in education?
13. How would you describe your interaction with the lecturers?
14. How does interaction between students take place, including those from different specialties considering that there are no formal study groups?
15. How do you see your future career? Did you study career planning? Do you associate your future with UFU?
16. When you became a project manager at UFU, which specific knowledge and skills gained during your studies helped you the most?
17. How often do students reach out to you? What kinds of questions do you help with?
18. What is the role of digitalization in your work? Do you use artificial intelligence in your job?
19. What are your priorities in your work? What do you consider the most important?
20. What mission do you think UFU is fulfilling in modern conditions?
21. What key words would you use to describe the uniqueness of studying at UFU?
22. What key words would you use to describe the uniqueness of working at UFU?
23. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the experience of preparation at UFU could be useful?

Appendix A7

Interview Guide with the Head of the Library and UFU Graduate, Ivan Zarytsky

1. What is your personal history of studying and working at UFU? What was your previous education?
2. How are the classes at UFU? What motivates you to study? What forms of work do you enjoy?
3. Which subjects do you remember the most?
4. Did you study subjects related to the socio-humanitarian curriculum?
5. Did you choose courses in psychology and pedagogy? If so, how did they enrich you, and what new knowledge and skills did you gain?
6. What is your experience of participating in educational projects?
7. What topic did you choose for your Master's thesis? What are the main requirements for it? How is the thesis writing progressing?
8. Did you participate in scientific conferences?
9. Do you have experience with publications?
10. How is the individual learning trajectory of students ensured?
11. What do you think is the role of the lecturer in modern student education? Which classes became the most significant for you?
12. What is the role of digitalization in modern student education? Have you used artificial intelligence in education?
13. How would you describe your interaction with the lecturers?
14. How does interaction between students take place, including those from different specialties considering that there are no formal study groups?
15. How do you see your future career? Did you study career planning? Do you associate your future with UFU?
16. When you became the head of the library, which specific knowledge and skills gained during your studies helped you the most?
17. What makes the UFU library unique? Can you provide any statistical data?
18. How frequently do library users access the library? Who uses the library most often?
19. What is the role of digitalization in your work? Do you use artificial intelligence in your job?
20. What are your priorities in your work? What do you consider the most important?
21. What mission do you think UFU is fulfilling in modern conditions?
22. What key words would you use to describe the uniqueness of studying at UFU?
23. What key words would you use to describe the uniqueness of working at UFU?
24. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the experience of teacher preparation at UFU could be useful?

Appendix A8

Interview Guide with the Archivist and Master's Student of UFU, Yulia Chernomor

1. What is your personal history of studying and working at UFU? What was your previous education?
2. How are the classes at UFU? What motivates you to study? What forms of work do you enjoy?
3. Which subjects do you remember the most?
4. Did you study subjects related to the socio-humanitarian curriculum (other than history, as it is your main specialty)?
5. Did you choose courses in psychology and pedagogy? If so, how did they enrich you, and what new knowledge and skills did you gain?
6. What is your experience of participating in educational projects?
7. What topic did you choose for your Master's thesis? What are the main requirements for it? How is the thesis writing progressing?
8. Did you participate in scientific conferences?
9. Do you have experience with publications?
10. How is the individual learning trajectory of students ensured?
11. What do you think is the role of the lecturer in modern student education? Which classes became the most significant for you?
12. What is the role of digitalization in modern student education? Have you used artificial intelligence in education?
13. How would you describe your interaction with the lecturers?
14. How does interaction between students take place, including those from different specialties considering that there are no formal study groups?
15. How do you see your future career? Did you study career planning? Do you associate your future with UFU?
16. When you became an archivist, which specific knowledge and skills gained during your studies helped you the most?
17. What makes the UFU archive unique? Can you provide any statistical data?
18. How frequently do library users access the archive? Who uses the archive most often?
19. What is the role of digitalization in your work? Do you use artificial intelligence in your job?
20. What are your priorities in your work? What do you consider the most important?
21. What mission do you think UFU is fulfilling in modern conditions?
22. What key words would you use to describe the uniqueness of studying at UFU?
23. What key words would you use to describe the uniqueness of working at UFU?
24. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the experience of preparation at UFU could be useful?

Appendix A9
Interview Guide with a Master's Student in "Pedagogy" Anna Higl

1. Please briefly tell us about yourself (where you were born, where you studied, how long you have been in Germany, and if you are working).
2. What is your personal history of studying at UFU? What was your previous education?
3. What distinguishes studying at UFU from studying at a university in Ukraine?
4. How are the classes at UFU? What motivates you to study? What forms of work do you enjoy?
5. Which subjects do you remember the most?
6. Did you study subjects related to the socio-humanitarian curriculum? If so, how did they enrich you, and what new knowledge and skills did you gain?
7. How did the courses in psychology and pedagogy enrich you, and what new knowledge and skills did you acquire?
8. What is your experience of participating in educational projects?
9. What topic did you choose for your Master's thesis? What are the main requirements for it? How is the thesis writing progressing?
10. Did you participate in scientific conferences?
11. Do you have experience with publications?
12. How is the individual learning trajectory of students ensured?
13. What do you think is the role of the lecturer in modern student education? Which classes became the most significant for you?
14. What is the role of digitalization in modern student education? Have you used artificial intelligence in your studies?
15. How would you describe your interaction with the lecturers?
16. How does interaction between students take place, including those from different specialties considering that there are no formal study groups?
17. Did you participate in volunteer activities?
18. How do you see your future career? Did you study career planning? Do you plan to continue your studies at UFU in the PhD preparation program? Do you plan to teach? Do you feel ready for teaching?
19. What specific knowledge and skills gained during your studies are useful in your work?
20. How is the educational and methodological support for studying the courses provided? How do you work with literature when preparing for classes?
21. What exactly makes studying at UFU unique?
22. What are your priorities in studying? What do you consider the most important?
23. What mission do you think UFU is fulfilling in modern conditions?
24. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the experience of preparing educators at UFU could be useful?

Appendix A10

Interview Guide with Viktoriia Danilevskaya

1. Please briefly tell us about yourself (where you were born, where you studied, how long you have been in Germany, and if you are working).
2. What is your personal history of studying at UFU? What was your previous education?
3. What distinguishes studying at UFU from studying at a university in Ukraine?
4. How are the classes at UFU? What motivates you to study? What forms of work do you enjoy?
5. Which subjects do you remember the most?
6. Did you study subjects related to the socio-humanitarian curriculum? If so, how did they enrich you, and what new knowledge and skills did you gain?
7. How did the courses in psychology and pedagogy enrich you, and what new knowledge and skills did you acquire?
8. What is your experience of participating in educational projects?
9. What topic did you choose for your dissertation? What are the main requirements for it? How is the thesis writing progressing?
10. Did you participate in scientific conferences?
11. Do you have experience with publications?
12. How is the individual learning trajectory of students ensured?
13. What do you think is the role of the lecturer in modern student education? Which classes became the most significant for you?
14. What is the role of digitalization in modern student education? Have you used artificial intelligence in your studies?
15. How would you describe your interaction with the lecturers?
16. How does interaction between students take place, including those from different specialties considering that there are no formal study groups?
17. Did you participate in volunteer activities?
18. How do you see your future career? Did you study career planning? Do you plan to continue your studies at UFU in the PhD preparation program? Do you plan to teach? Do you feel ready for teaching?
19. What specific knowledge and skills gained during your studies are useful in your work?
20. How is the educational and methodological support for studying the courses provided? How do you work with literature when preparing for classes?
21. What exactly makes studying at UFU unique?
22. What are your priorities in studying? What do you consider the most important?
23. What mission do you think UFU is fulfilling in modern conditions?
24. What recommendations for Ukrainian universities regarding the experience of preparing educators at UFU could be useful?

Appendix B.
Decision of the Academic Council of the Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine “On the results of the project “Analysis of Pedagogical Studies of the Ukrainian Free University in Germany” under the DAAD program “Ukraine’s Future: Research Grants for Ukrainian Master's Students and Researchers”

RESOLUTION

of the Academic Council of the Institute of Vocational Education
of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine

March 17, 2025.
Protocol № 3

**About the results of the project
"Analysis of pedagogical studies
of the Ukrainian Free University
in Germany" under the DAAD programme
"The future of Ukraine: research grants
for Ukrainian Master's students and researchers"**

Having heard the information from the leading researcher of the Department of Foreign Systems of Vocational Education G. M. Romanova, on the results of the project "Analysis of Pedagogical Studies of the Ukrainian Free University in Germany" under the DAAD program "Ukraine’s Future: Research Grants for Ukrainian Master’s Students and Researchers," the Academic Council

RESOLVES:

1. Take note of the information on the results of the project "Analysis of Pedagogical Studies of the Ukrainian Free University in Germany" under the DAAD program "Ukraine’s Future: Research Grants for Ukrainian Master's Students and Researchers" (attached).
2. Facilitate the dissemination of the project results during scientific and practical events of the Institute of Vocational Education of the NAES of Ukraine.
3. Ensure systematic cooperation within the framework of the signed agreement with the Ukrainian Free University (Munich, Germany).
4. Enhance international mobility of the research staff of the Institute of Vocational Education of the NAES of Ukraine.
5. Assign responsibility for monitoring the implementation of this decision to the Deputy Director for Research, M. A. Pryhodii, the Deputy Director for Scientific and Experimental Work, L. M. Yershova, and the Academic Secretary, L. O. Bazyl.

Chair of the Academic Council

Valentina RADKEVYCH

Academic Council Scientific Secretary

Lyudmyla BAZYI

Appendix C. Agreement on international cooperation

N 1-1/2025

AGREEMENT
on international cooperation
between
the Institute of Vocational Education of
the National Academy of Educational
Sciences of Ukraine and the Ukrainian
Free University (Germany)

from 19.02. 2025

The Institute of Vocational Education of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, represented by the Director of the Institute, **Valentyna Radkevych**, on the one hand, and the Ukrainian Free University, represented by the Rector of the University, **Larysa Didkovska**, on the other hand (hereinafter referred to as the Parties),

Noting the unified approach in understanding the importance of international cooperation and partnership in: strengthening scientific ties between Ukrainian and German scientific institutions and scientists; synchronizing the Parties' activities to increase the prestige and development of European higher education; studying best educational practices to popularize and protect common European values,

striving to ensure maximum effectiveness of the measures taken in achieving common goals,
have concluded this Agreement and agreed as follows:

Article 1. Purpose and subject of the Agreement

1.1. The purpose of this Agreement is: to consolidate the efforts of the Parties aimed at popularizing in Ukraine the European principles of the functioning of educational systems, familiarizing European scientists with the national characteristics of the Ukrainian education system, and developing joint approaches to ensuring the socio-humanitarian development of future specialists as representatives of the free democratic world.

1.2. The subject of this Agreement is the coordination of efforts and joint activities of the Parties to achieve the goal of the Agreement, which is carried out in the format of preparation and implementation of joint activities and projects.

ДОГОВІР
про міжнародне співробітництво
між Інститутом професійної освіти
Національної академії педагогічних
наук України та
Українським Вільним Університетом
(Німеччина)

від 19.02. 2025 року

Інститутом професійної освіти Національної академії педагогічних наук України в особі директора Інституту **Валентини Радкевич**, з однієї сторони, та Українським Вільним Університетом Мюнхена в особі ректора Університету **Лариси Дідковської**, з іншої сторони (далі разом – Сторони),

констатуючи єдиний підхід у розумінні значимості міжнародної співпраці і партнерства щодо: зміцнення наукових зв'язків між українськими та німецькими науковими установами і вченими; синхронізації заходів Сторін з підвищення престижу і розвитку європейської вищої освіти; вивчення кращих освітніх практик з популяризації і захисту спільних європейських цінностей,

прагнучи забезпечити максимальну ефективність здійснюваних заходів при досягненні спільних цілей,

уклали цей Договір та домовилися про таке:

Стаття 1. Мета і предмет Договору

1.1. Метою цього Договору є: консолідація зусиль Сторін, спрямованих на популяризацію в Україні європейських принципів функціонування освітніх систем, ознайомлення європейських учених з національними особливостями української системи освіти, вироблення спільних підходів до забезпечення соціогуманітарного розвитку майбутніх фахівців як представників вільного демократичного світу.

1.2. Предметом цього Договору є координація зусиль та спільна діяльність Сторін задля досягнення мети Договору, що здійснюється у форматі підготовки та реалізації спільних заходів та проєктів.

Article 2. Areas of cooperation between the Parties

2.1. In order to achieve the goal of this Agreement, the Parties agree on cooperation in the following areas:

2.1.1. Development and implementation of joint projects and/or programs, conducting research aimed at popularizing European values and Ukrainian educational and cultural traditions.

2.1.2. Organization of joint events through conferences, seminars, round tables, meetings and other public events.

2.1.3. Mutual assistance in the development of academic mobility of scientists and students of the Parties.

2.1.4. Mutual assistance in the development of publishing activities of scientists by involving them in publication in periodicals of the Parties.

2.1.5. Strengthening scientific cooperation between members of the editorial boards of periodicals of the Parties.

2.1.6. Participation in the development and implementation of projects to improve the quality of education, improve the educational process in educational institutions based on the introduction of new pedagogical technologies, informatization, and strengthening the organic unity of students' learning with the practice;

2.1.7. Promoting joint mass events aimed at educating responsible citizens, aware of the synergy of professional, universal and national values, education of highly qualified specialists, and forming the socially active, morally and physically healthy, proactive educational potential of Ukraine and Germany;

2.1.8. Coverage and promotion of the Parties' activities;

2.2. Other agreed areas of cooperation.

Article 3. Forms of cooperation between the Parties

3.1. The Parties to the Agreement declare their agreement and readiness to accept the following obligations:

3.1.1. actively and promptly cooperate on the basis of partnership, mutual assistance and mutual support;

3.1.2. to contribute to the creation of a favorable legal, organizational, informational and material environment for cooperation between the Parties;

3.1.3. support each other's initiatives aimed at developing partnership between the Parties, as well as at fulfilling the main tasks of the Parties,

Стаття 2. Напрями співпраці Сторін

2.1. Задля досягнення мети цього Договору Сторони домовляються про співпрацю за такими напрямками:

2.1.1. Розроблення та реалізація спільних проєктів та/або програм, проведення досліджень, спрямованих на популяризацію європейських цінностей та українських освітньо-культурних традицій.

2.1.2. Організація спільних заходів шляхом проведення конференцій, семінарів, круглих столів, зустрічей та інших публічних заходів.

2.1.3. Взаємне сприяння розвитку академічної мобільності науковців і здобувачів освіти Сторін.

2.1.4. Взаємне сприяння розвитку публікаційної активності науковців шляхом їх залучення до публікації у періодичних виданнях Сторін.

2.1.5. Посилення наукової співпраці членів редакційних колегій періодичних видань Сторін.

2.1.6. Участь у розробленні й реалізації проєктів з підвищення якості освіти, удосконалення освітнього процесу в закладах освіти на основі впровадження нових педагогічних технологій, інформатизації, посилення органічної єдності навчання з практикою здобувачів освіти;

2.1.7. Сприяння проведенню спільних масових заходів з метою виховання відповідальних громадян, свідомих синергії професійних, загальнолюдських і національних цінностей, підготовки фахівців високого кваліфікаційного рівня, формування соціально активного, морально й фізично здорового, проактивного педагогічного потенціалу України та Німеччини;

2.1.8. Висвітлення й популяризація діяльності Сторін;

2.2. Інші узгоджені напрями співпраці.

Стаття 3. Форми співпраці Сторін

3.1. Сторони Договору заявляють про згоду та готовність прийняти наступні зобов'язання:

3.1.1. активно й оперативно співпрацювати на основі партнерства, взаємодопомоги та взаємної підтримки;

3.1.2. сприяти створенню сприятливого правового, організаційного, інформаційного та матеріального середовища для співпраці Сторін;

3.1.3. підтримувати ініціативи одна одної, спрямовані на розвиток партнерства між Сторонами, а також на виконання основних

increasing the level of efficiency, professionalism and coordination of their activities at the levels of all structural bodies of the Parties;

3.1.4. in order to increase the efficiency of the activities of the Parties, as well as cooperation between them, to ensure information exchange regarding the activities of the Parties;

3.1.5. organize joint, including public, events to discuss current issues, as well as events aimed at exchanging experience between the Parties.

Article 4. Organization of cooperation between the Parties

4.1. In order to implement this Agreement, the Parties, within the limits of available resources:

4.1.1. identify contact persons for consultations and development of proposals for the joint implementation of tasks and activities defined by this Agreement;

4.1.2. hold meetings to discuss issues related to the implementation of the Agreement, exchange information on the activities of the Parties in the area defined by the Agreement;

4.1.3. develop and jointly approve plans for joint activities;

4.1.4. undertake to maintain the confidentiality of personal information that has become known in connection with the implementation of the Memorandum, in particular in accordance with the requirements of the legislation of Ukraine and Germany.

4.1.5. undertake to refrain from actions that may cause moral, economic or other damage to the other Party.

Article 5. Final provisions

5.1. This Agreement shall enter into force on the date of its signing by the Parties and shall be concluded for a period of five years. The Agreement shall be automatically extended for the next term unless either Party notifies the other Party in writing of its intention to terminate the Agreement no later than three months prior to its termination.

5.2. The Parties may terminate this Agreement early at any time by notifying the other Party in writing.

5.3. In the case of termination of this Agreement, activities that were initiated on the basis of the Agreement and not completed during its term shall continue and be completed in accordance with the terms previously agreed upon by the Parties, except in cases where it is impossible to complete these activities.

завдань сторін, підвищення рівня ефективності, професіоналізму та злагодженості їх діяльності на рівнях усіх структурних органів Сторін;

3.1.4. з метою підвищення ефективності діяльності Сторін, а також співпраці між ними забезпечувати інформаційний обмін щодо діяльності Сторін;

3.1.5. організовувати спільні, в тому числі, публічні заходи для обговорення актуальних питань, а також заходи, спрямовані на обмін досвідом між Сторонами.

Стаття 4. Організація співпраці Сторін

4.1. З метою реалізації цього Договору Сторони в межах наявних ресурсів:

4.1.1. визначають контактних осіб для проведення консультацій і розроблення пропозицій щодо спільної реалізації завдань та заходів, визначених цим Договором;

4.1.2. проводять зустрічі з метою обговорення питань щодо реалізації Договору, обміну інформацією про діяльність Сторін у визначеній Договором сфері;

4.1.3. розробляють та спільно затверджують плани спільних заходів;

4.1.4. беруть на себе зобов'язання зберігати конфіденційність персональної інформації, що стала відома у зв'язку з реалізацією Договору, зокрема відповідно до вимог законодавства України і Німеччини.

4.1.5. беруть на себе зобов'язання утримуватись від дій, що можуть заподіяти моральну, економічну чи іншу шкоду іншій Стороні.

Стаття 5. Прикінцеві положення

5.1. Цей Договір набирає чинності з дня його підписання Сторонами та укладається строком на п'ять років. Дія Договору автоматично продовжується на наступний термін, якщо жодна зі Сторін не пізніше як за три місяці до припинення дії Договору письмово не повідомить іншу Сторону про свій намір припинити його дію.

5.2. Сторони можуть достроково припинити дію цього Договору у будь-який час, письмово повідомивши про це іншу Сторону.

5.3. У разі припинення дії цього Договору заходи, що були розпочаті на підставі Договору і не завершені протягом терміну його дії, продовжуються і завершуються згідно з умовами, що були раніше погоджені Сторонами, за винятком випадків, коли завершити ці заходи неможливо.

5.4. Any amendments and additions to this Agreement shall be made only with the written consent of the Parties and shall remain its integral part.

5.5. Any disputes regarding the interpretation or application of the provisions of this Agreement shall be resolved by the Parties on an amicable basis through consultations and negotiations.

5.6. The Agreement is drafted in two copies, in Ukrainian and English, which have equal legal force, with one copy for each Party.

5.4. Будь-які зміни і доповнення до цього Договору вносяться тільки за письмовою згодою Сторін і стають його невід'ємною частиною.

5.5. Будь-які спірні питання щодо тлумачення або застосування положень цього Договору вирішуються Сторонами на дружній основі шляхом проведення консультацій і переговорів.

5.6. Договір складений в двох примірниках українською і англійською мовою, що мають однакову юридичну силу, по одному примірнику для кожної Сторони.

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Director
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